

Investigation on Antimicrobial Activity of Sein-pan-gale Flowers

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Abstract

The flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* L. (Sein-pan-gale) were chosen for the investigation of the antimicrobial activity. The phytochemical constituents present in the sample were also determined. The preliminary phytochemical tests indicated the presence of alkaloids, α - amino acids, carbohydrates, glycosides, phenolic compounds, saponin glycosides, steroids, tannins, terpenoids and flavonoids in the plant sample. Cyanogenic glycosides which generally possess toxic property were not detected. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity was determined by agar well diffusion method. It was observed that the crude extracts (PE, EtOH, H₂O) of the plant samples exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against all tested microorganisms: *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus pumalis*, *Candida albican* and *Escherichia coli*.

Keywords: Sein-pan-gale, Phytochemical Tests, Antimicrobial Activity

Introduction

The pharmacological evaluation of substances from plants is an established method for the identification of lead compounds which can leads to the development of novel and safe medicinal agents (website:1). Most of people use the traditional medicinal plants for the treatment of diseases. Although synthetic drugs and antibiotic drugs brought about a revolution in controlling different diseases, plants occupy a very significant place as raw materials for some important drugs (Medicinal plants of Myanmar, 2000).

In the present research, the flowers of Sein-pan-gale (*Caesalpinia pulcherrima* L.) were chosen for the investigation of antimicrobial activity by using *in vitro* agar well diffusion method.

Sein-pan-gale (*Caesalpinia pulcherrima* L.) is a striking ornamental plant (Figure: 1) widely grown in domestic and public gardens and has a beautiful inflorescence in yellow, red and orange (website: 4). It is native to tropical America. In India, it is found in the tropical rain forests (website: 2). In Myanmar, it can be seen in many places.

Figure (1) Sein-pan-gale Plant

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Materials and Method

Preparation of Sample

In this research, Sein-pan-gale flowers were collected from the Mingaladon township in Yangon, Myanmar. The botanical name was identified as *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* L. by authorized botanists at Botany Department, Bago University in Bago, Myanmar. The collected plant samples were washed with water to remove impurities. They were dried at room temperature to prevent some reactions of the organic constituents present in samples with sun light. The air-dried plant samples were cut into pieces and ground in grinding mill to get a coarse powder. The powdered samples were stored in the air-tight containers for the experimental works such as phytochemical tests and the preparation of the crude extracts.

Preliminary Phytochemical Tests and Preparation of Crude Extracts

The preliminary phytochemical tests were carried out according to the standard procedures (Trease, 1980). The results obtained were shown in Table (1).

Ethanol extract from Sein-pan-gale flowers was prepared by percolation method. The air-dried powdered sample (ca- 100 g) was extracted with 70% ethanol (500 ml) for about one week and then filtered. The extraction and filtration processes were carried out for three times. The combined filtrates were concentrated under vacuum rotary evaporator to get ethanol crude extract. PE extract of Sein-pan-gale flowers was also prepared by the same way as that of ethanol extract.

In the preparation of watery extract, 300 g of the dried powdered sample was soaked in distilled water (1000 cm³) in the conical flask. The flask was boiled on a water bath for 6 hours and filtered. This process was carried out for three times. The combined filtrates were evaporated to dryness over a water bath at 100°C to get the watery extract.

Screening on Antimicrobial Activity of Sein-pan-gale Flowers

In-vitro antimicrobial activity determinations for the crude extracts (PE, EtOH and H₂O) of Sein-pan-gale flowers were carried out by using agar well diffusion method.

In this method, PE, EtOH and aqueous extracts of Sein-pan-gale flowers were used as the samples. The extract (1 g each) was introduced into sterile petridish and dissolved in 1ml or with least amount of its respective solvent (PE or EtOH or distilled water) till it was dissolved. The bacteria suspension from trypticase soy broth was done evenly onto the surface of the trypticase soy agar plates immediately after hardening of the agar well were made with a 10mm sterile cork bore from each needed agar. After inoculum had dried for 5 minutes, the agar disks were removed and the wells were filled with sample to be tested. And then, the plates were incubated at 37°C. After overnight incubation at 37°C, the diameter of inhibition zone including 10 mm was measured.

The well plate dilution method was used to test antimicrobial activities of the extracts on 24 hours broth culture of the organism used. Various crude extracts (PE, EtOH and H₂O) of Sein-pan-gale flowers were tested with the following microorganisms: *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus pumalis*, *Candida albican* and *Escherichia coli* species. The results obtained were noted and presented in Table (2).

Results and Discussion

According to the results obtained from the phytochemical investigations, it was observed that steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, glycosides, α - amino acids, alkaloids and saponin glycosieds were found to be present in

Sein-pan-gale flowers. Cyanogenic glycosides which generally possess toxic property were not detected in the plant sample.

The crude extracts (PE, EtOH and H₂O) of Sein-pan-gale flowers were prepared by employing the successive percolation method. It was found that the amount of non-polar constituents present in PE extract of Sein-pan-gale flowers were 26.84 %. It was also found that polar constituents present in EtOH extract were 35.53 % and the water soluble contents were found to be 28.72 %.

The antimicrobial activity of the crude extracts (PE, EtOH and H₂O) was investigated against six species of microorganisms by employing agar well diffusion method. The tested microorganisms were *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus pumalis*, *Candida albican* and *Escherichia coli*. The results were shown in Table (2) and Figure (2).

According to the results in Table (2), it was found that PE extracts (12~15 mm), EtOH extracts (13~18 mm) and H₂O extracts (12~ 16 mm) of Sein-pan-gale flowers exhibited pronounced antimicrobial activity against all tested microorganisms. So, it may be inferred that the crude extracts (PE, EtOH, H₂O) of Sein-pan-gale flowers can be effective in the formulation of medicine for the treatment of diseases such as diarrhea, fevers, bladder and kidney inflammation, and urinary dysfunctions.

Table (1) Results for the Phytochemical Tests of Sein-pan-gale Flowers

No.	Compound	Extract	Reagent	Indication	Observation
1	Alkaloids	1% HCl	Dragendroff's reagent Mayer's reagent Sodium picrate solution Wagner's reagent	Pink ppt White ppt Red ppt Reddish brown ppt	+
2	α - Amino acids	H ₂ O	Ninhydrin solution	Purple spot	+
3	Carbohydrates	H ₂ O	10% α -Naphthol, H ₂ SO ₄	Red ring	+
4	Cyanogenic glycosides	H ₂ O	Sodium picrate solution	No color	-
5	Flavonoids	H ₂ O	Benzene, EtOH solution	Yellow color	+
6	Glycosides	H ₂ O	10% Lead acetate	White ppt	+
7	Phenolic compounds	H ₂ O	1% FeCl ₃ solution	White ppt	+
8	Reducing sugars	H ₂ O	Fehling solution	Orange ppt	+
9	Saponin glycosides	H ₂ O	Water	Foam	+
10	Tannins	H ₂ O	1% Gelatin 1% FeCl ₃ solution	Brick red color White ppt	+
11	Terpenoids/ Steroids	H ₂ O	Acetic anhydride, H ₂ SO ₄	Blue color	+

(+) = present, (-) = absent

Table (2) Results for Antimicrobial Activity of Sein-pan-gale Flower Extracts on Six microorganisms

Solvent Extract	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
EtOH	17mm	13mm	15mm	15mm	18mm	15mm
PE	12mm	12mm	13mm	12mm	15mm	12mm
H ₂ O	15mm	12mm	13mm	12mm	16mm	14mm

Organisms

Agar well - 7mm

7 mm - 11mm (+)

12 mm - 16 mm (++)

17mm - above (+++)

(1) *Bacillus Subtilis*(2) *Staphylococcus aureus*(3) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*(4) *Bacillus pumalis*(5) *Candida albican*(6) *E-Coli***Microorganism**

1. *Bacillus subtilis*
2. *Staphylococcus aureus*
3. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
4. *Bacillus pumalis*
5. *Candida albican*
6. *Escherichia coli*

- a. EtOH control
- b. PE control
- c. H₂O control
- d. PE extract
- e. H₂O extract
- f. EtOH extract

Figure (2) Effects of Sein-pan-gale Flower Extracts on Six Microorganisms

Conclusion

According to the literature, Myanmar medicinal plant Sein-pan-gale can be used to treat diabetes, urinary problems, diarrhea, malarial fever, hypercholesterolemia and as antioxidant. By studying the results obtained from the present investigation on the antimicrobial activity of Sein-pan-gale flowers, it was observed that all of the crude extracts exhibited significant antimicrobial activity. The effect of the EtOH extract is more pronounced than the other two extracts. From these observations, it may be concluded that the ethanol extract of plant sample may be more effective in formulation of medicines to treat the diseases such as diarrhea, urinary tract infection, inflammations, eye-infection and wound sepsis.

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